

Design Thinking for New Product Development (Leradia Case Study)

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ABSTRACT: The development of a new product is an important thing to do for developing a business, moreover in the fashion business industry. New product development can determine how an organization brings off its succession, such as in sales and profit. The new product development can bring 50% sales and 40% of profits for an organization. The new product development needs to be done to fulfill the customer's needs and wants and complete their demand for a product. As a new business, Leradia as a modest fashion business from Indonesia has not generated a unique perspective from customers and has not understood the Leradia persona as well as their pain and gain. Thus, in order to avoid the failure of a new business, connect with customers, and compete in the market, Leradia aims to understand Leradia customer pain and gain and get to know what kind of development. Qualitative methods are used by interviewing six of Leradia's most loyal customers to develop an understanding of Leradia's customers. Adopted the study methodology of design thinking there are five stages to proceed with the data gathered; Empathizing, Defining, Ideate, Prototype, and Test. Starting from analyzing the customer persona until the proposed product development and testing the proposed solution to the customer to get the customer feedback and point of view.

KEYWORDS: Design Thinking, Modest Fashion Brand, Product Development.

INTRODUCTION

In this dynamic and fast-changing business environment, the relevance of national and multinational businesses' value propositions continues to grow. As a result, there is a high demand for innovative patterns of thinking and methodologies for developing innovative value propositions. Design thinking is a naturally user-centric method of thought that promotes the production of value propositions. Today's businesses need to generate unique ideas to maintain relevance and obtain competitive advantages in a variety of fragmented marketplaces characterized by impermanence, hyper-competitiveness, globalization, and fluidity. To stay competitive in the global fashion industry market, the fashion industry must increase the speed at which they supply their products to clients to adapt to market shifts. The fashion industry has a short life cycle, significant volatility, little predictability, and a high percentage of impulse purchases (Christopher, Lawson, & Peck, 2004). Therefore, new product development is required to determine a fashion company's performance relative to its competitors. New product development is a critical activity that companies must perform (Stalk Jr., 1998).

The development of a new product is an important thing to do for developing a business, moreover in the fashion business industry. New product development can determine how an organization brings off its succession, such as in sales and profit. The new product development can bring 50% sales and 40% of profits for an organization (Cooper, Doing it Right: Winning with New Products, 2000). The new product development needs to be done to fulfill the customer's needs and wants and complete their demand for a product. To have a successful market, the company must clearly define the customer's needs and wants through the product at a suitable price (Gangurde & Akarte, 2015). To obtain the required results, further studies can be conducted. Consumer needs and desires for a product might be utilized to guide research. Therefore, a study was conducted on the business of Modest Fashion products in Leradia's Official modest fashion.

BUSINESS OVERVIEW AND ITS CHALLENGES

Leradia was founded in 2020 as a modest fashion brand that supports women's modesty attire, such as Hijab/Scarves, Prayer Set, Abaya dresses, and other modest attire. However, oftentimes the internal of Leradia's company gets an excessive amount of time discussing product creation from deciding the material, and design until the details because the two owners and employees have diverse interests in creating products. From the very beginning, Leradia has produced items that were created only based on the owner's preferences without considering and understanding what the customer exactly needs and wants. Until now their product

variations are still limited, still lacking variants in design, color, size and number of stock. Especially the Prayer Set product, which has the fewest variants, they only have one design with three colors. The Abaya Dresses have six designs, the Signature Hijab Swarovski products have sixteen variant colors with two Swarovski pattern designs, the Voile Hijab has variant colors, and all of these product stock is still limited. Besides having the fewest variant, Leradia's Prayer Set products also have the lowest sales among the other product. It can be shown in Figure 1. Leradia Product Sales 2021.

Figure 1. Leradia Product Sales 2021

It can be seen that the Prayer Set had the lowest sales among the other product even until now. In the first quarter, the Prayer Set sold only 40 pcs whereas the Hijab Signature sold 99 pcs, Hijab Voile sold 91 pcs, and Abaya Dress sold 57 pcs. In the second quarter, the Prayer Set sold improved to 50 pcs where the Hijab Signature sold 100 pcs, Hijab Voile sold 91 pcs, and Abaya Dress sold 57 pcs. In the third quarter, the Prayer Set sold decreased to 36 pcs where the Hijab Signature sold 101 pcs, Hijab Voile sold 81 pcs, and Abaya Dress sold 49 pcs. And in the fourth quarter, the Prayer Set sold only 29 pcs whereas the Hijab Signature sold 89 pcs, Hijab Voile sold 91 pcs, and Abaya Dress sold 57 pcs.

To comprehend the hidden pattern of unmet customer expectations between the Leradia Prayer Set product offering and its customers, it is necessary to dig deeper into Leradia customer needs as a way of identifying problems. The potential is very high that many more potential products will arise from the pain and gain experienced by customers. Leradia has made no attempt, to begin with the most fundamental wants and concerns expressed by its clients. By gaining this knowledge, Leradia can design new products that address all customer needs, enabling it to remain competitive and thrive in a highly competitive industry.

Companies today face a need to generate unique perspectives in order to acquire competitive advantages and remain relevant in numerous fragmented marketplaces characterized by impermanence, hyper-competition, globalization, and fluidity. To provide value for customers and improve their experience, dynamic thinking styles such as design thinking are essential (Tuominen and Ascenço, 2016). Meanwhile, Leradia has not generated a unique perspective from customers and has not understood the Leradia persona as well as their pain and gain. Thus, in order to avoid the failure of a new business, connect with customers, and to compete in the market, Leradia aims to understand Leradia customer pain and gain and get to know what kind of development that Leradia needs to propose in order to solve the customer problem. Design as a strategic tool for company development has become a hot topic among scientists and practitioners over the last decade (Prahalad, 2004)

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- The objective of this research is to identifying Leradia's customer needs and issues related to wearing Prayer Set product experiences and create a strategic plan for the Prayer Set product development to contribute to the long-term sales.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

○ The researcher adopted the study methodology of design thinking to proceed the data gathered. Starting with empathizing, the researcher finds out the real problem that is trying to solve by using Personas canvas to guide in an in-depth interview. After gathering any information from emphasizing, synthesize to define the real problem of the users by using the Customer Journey Map and Value proposition canvas and start to look at the problem statement to create any out-of-the-box possible solutions in the Ideate phase. Then, the idea or innovation can be tested because this step is about prototyping. The last but very important step is to test the implementation strategy.

Figure 2. Design Thinking Framework

A. Research Method

There are various approaches that can be utilized to collect data during the research process. The qualitative method is used as the primary data collection methodology in this study. Qualitative research is a method that enables an in-depth examination of people's experiences (Hennink et al. 2011: 8). The qualitative method is used as the primary data collection methodology in this study. Qualitative research is a method that enables an in-depth examination of people's experiences (Hennink et al. 2011: 8). Using primary data, and literature review gathering from books, journals, industry reports, news, websites, or online review platforms for data collecting. The initial phase in this research is to obtain the new products or feature value proposition canvas. This research aims to learn deeply about the customer or target market, what their pain points are with the existing product, and what they would like to see changed. The qualitative method is used as the primary data collection methodology in this study.

B. Data Collection Method

This research uses a qualitative method of an in-depth interview. An in-depth interview is related to a conversation in that it involves two individuals discussing a topic of mutual interest in a relaxed, open, and transparent manner (Mason, 1998). Obtaining a real sense of the customer's emotions and experience with a product or feature can be accomplished through an open and honest conversation, as supported by Mason's theory. By that point, the outcome of this study should be a genuine answer to the customer's real root issue, rather than a guess or an assumption about what the customer truly needs.

FINDING AND ANALYSIS

To propose the priorities for product realization and proposed product development, following the analysis of their interview with customers by understanding Leradia's customers' pains and gains related to the Prayer Set product and determining the development of new products that can be proposed:

A. *Emphasize - Persona*

According to Scott (2007), the buyer persona's function toward a business is to develop a plan for the promotion and marketing of the company's products or services to the defined group and type of individuals. From the interview result, three personas were successfully created; Persona 1 Vanya, Persona 2 Agatha and Persona 3 Arafa. Vanya usually prays Dzuhur and Ashar at her office, bringing her own Prayer Set and Prayer Mat is mandatory for her. She loves Silk material Prayer sets, but sometimes it is easy to get water stains after *wudu*. She also has another problem when she uses a Prayer Set, like it is hard to find the hood strap that fits her head well. Sometimes the strap is loose. Vanya likes to buy Prayer sets or other fashion products both online and offline, a payment installment service would be preferable for her.

Agatha loves to go outside like hang out or travel abroad, she needs a Prayer Set with travel size, pastel-colored, and elegant design, So she can pray solemnly anywhere without having to spend a lot of space in her bag. Agatha loves to visit an offline store nearby if she wants to know the real quality of the product. She also likes to scroll through Instagram, Shopee, and Tiktokshop almost every day, besides that she likes to buy branded products from abroad.

Arafa needs Prayer Set with cool material, elegant, neutral color, and gentle so she can pray comfortably. Arafa is taller than the average height of women in Indonesia, thus she needs a quite bigger size of Prayer Set. When she is brought online, sometimes she gets disappointed with the product because the product is not the same as the picture.

B. *Define*

Once persona data is analyzed, it will be better to understand the customer's experience and pain points. These processes help researchers in classifying the information and structurally differentiating fact from bias. The purpose of this essential phase involves the formulation of a problem statement and an actionable problem statement. By empathizing with an increasing number of people, observers will begin to notice a pattern. Observers can deduce the majority of people's spot problems based on the pattern they read.

This phase will focus more on creating all the components to produce a solution for business issues through a value proposition canvas. The value proposition describes the expected benefits of a product or service. (Osterwalder, Pigneur, Bernanda & Smith, 2014). The customer profile consists of three blocks: customer job to be done, pain, and gain, while the value map consists of products and services, gain generators, and pain relievers. If Customer Profile and Value Map match each other, then this relationship is said to be fit.

1. *Customer Job to be Done*

The customer profile describes the specific market segment of the company's model in order to produce a complete and organized profile (Dewobroto, 2016.). There are six customer jobs generated above that are already ranked based on the most essential, and each one of these jobs represents a different task that is usually done by the customer. Leradia's customer job to be done is choosing their best prayer set beside to fulfill obligations as a Muslim pray 5 times a day, intended to feel good, feel calm dan pray solemnly anywhere because prayer set also plays a big part. Since Leradia's persona usually pray Dzuhur and Ashar outside, thus choosing the best material, design and price is their priority. There are also emotional jobs like feeling comfortable wearing a particular prayer set.

2. *Pains*

Customer pains relate to anything that causes customers discomfort in order to complete a task. Pain could be a risk or any potential results, such as a job that could not be completed or finished poorly (Osterwalder, Pigneur, Bernanda, & Smith, 2014). There are thirteen customer pains generated that are already ranked based on, and each one of these pains represents a different pain that is usually experienced by the Leradia persona. Based on the interview, Leradia customers' pain mainly came from undesired outcomes starting from unfitted cutting or unmatched size, uncomfortable material like stifflingly hot material, limited design option, and no travel-friendly design so they could not bring into small bags and also they did not provide prayer mat. The obstacles faced are that

the picture that the seller posted on their social media sometimes is not the same as the real product, the expensive price, the colours offered are limited and sometimes it does not match customers' preference, and also the limited payment option.

3. Gains

Gains illustrate what customers want as an outcome and the benefit that might be required, expedited, or might be unexpected. It includes function utility, positive emotion, social benefit, or cost saving. The interview result concluded that Leradia's persona loves elegant material and design with affordable size. It is also mentioned that the prayer set should be a durable material. For Leadia's persona who loves shiny material, elegant design and material also it should comfort them and provide coolness to their head. For expected gain, customers expect unique details, like embroidered logos, and metal stitching accent, or unique bag. Last, the customer's desired gain is eco-friendly like zero-waste design, they will feel proud when knowing the product was zero-waste designed.

C. Ideate

Ideation is the process of responding to customer pains and gains. The strategy adopted in ideation was founder-led brainstorming to transform customers' feedback into a buildable proposition. Generating ideas from each participant in the design thinking process. Begin by examining the problem in order to generate any out-of-the-box solutions. Several alternate solutions may be examined as potential innovations. Brainstorming can be used to collect all of the ideas from each design thinker's background.

1. Pain Reliever

The pain reliever describes how a product or service helps relieve a customer's pain. It focuses on the pain that matters to customers and how products or services eliminate or reduce the pain that restricts their productivity or their work. Based on the interview and the analyzed data previously, the biggest pain for Leradia's customers was the unmatched size. Besides that, researchers also found that Leradia customers oftentimes experienced unmatched size of prayer set, like the hijab does not fit well to their head size and the skirt is loose and too long, it is easy to step on it, thus it disturb their prayer and become not solemn and even has to be repeated.

I. Alternative 1

This alternative focused on solving the unmatched size, expensive price, lack of review content, and lack of payment options. Based on brainstorming results with the Leradia team, here are the Pain Relievers from Leradia customer pains for an alternative:

- a. Adding more sizes like XS, S, M, L, XL, and XXL with detailed sizing description.
- b. Provides consultation about sizing.
- c. Provides sample products to try on in the change room at Leradia offline booth.
- d. Provides free service for cutting materials of Leradia prayer set.
- e. Provides promotion, and membership cards, like getting a minimum transaction of IDR 500.000 getting a voucher of IDR 50.000 on the next payment.
- f. Provides product reviews, product pictures, and video content not only from the seller itself but also from the customers and the Key Opinion Leader (KOL) sight.
- g. Provides customer testimonials.
- h. Provides installment payment service, and COD method.

One of the expectations of these alternatives is to make the customer feel comfortable when they are wearing the Leradia prayer set and all the aurat will be covered neatly, thus they can pray solemnly without the distraction of prayer set discomfort. Besides that is to make customers convenient in the payment process, and could afford the comfortable prayer set at an affordable price.

II. Alternative 2

The second alternative will focus on the next customer pain which is uncomfortable material like; stiflingly hot material, and easy to get water stain. And the second one is limited design and colour like; lack of variety of design, lack of colour preferences, and not provide travel friendly that can fit into small bags. Both of these pains are closely related to material and design, thus based on the Leradia team brainstorming results, the following are pain relievers for alternative 2:

- a. Provides a variety of designs;
 - A set of travel packages that consist of a prayer set (skirt and hijab).

- A set of travel packages that consist of a set of prayer sets (headless poncho practical prayer set).
 - Provide a variety of lace.
- b. Provides a variety of color tones and patterns;
- Provides pastel colour, bold colour, earth tone colour, and basic colour.
 - Provides a pattern on the prayer mat.
 - Provides Premium material;
 - Premium Korean Silk Parasites material for travel-size material.
 - Premium Silk anti-water stain for travel size.
 - Premium Armani Silk anti-water stain for non-travel size.
- c. Provided fastened by strap both on the hijab strap and strap at the waist of the skirt, so the size can be adjusted according to the size of the user.

These are the brainstorming results in the effort to solve Leradia customer's problems, these alternatives are expected to make the Leradia customer feel comfortable when praying by wearing the best material of Leradia prayer set and also to meet the desired outcomes of the Leradia's customers.

2. Gain Creator

Gain creators explain how the products and services produce the advantage for the consumer, with the goal of delivering our products and the benefits that the customer expects, desires, or will be positively surprised to see. This only needs to concentrate on the customer gains where the decision to offer products or services can make a meaningful difference.

I. Alternative 1

By improving existing products and services it is expected that the gain creators can be raised to the desired customer gain. From the brainstorming result, the first alternative is mostly about the new services, following are the first gain creators for alternatives 1:

- a. Provides thank you card letters for supporting zero-waste design products.
- b. Provides washing and care instructions.
- c. Activate the online customer service, maintain the relationship with customers, handle and collect feedback from customers and offer the promotion to the customers.
- d. Provides QR code cards which connect to Leradia's Instagram to offline store buyers.
- e. Provides video content about how to take care of the product.
- f. Provides video content about the advantage of wearing Leradia's prayer set.
- g. Provides hampers package by request

II. Alternative 2

The second alternative is to improve existing products. Following are Leradia's gain creators for alternatives 2:

- a. Improve the material to be Premium Armani silk with anti-water stain and anti-wrinkle.
- b. Provides unique details.
- c. Provides laser cutting design.

As a result of the brainstorming session, there are four potential gain creators for alternative 2, all of which are anticipated to provide solutions to the issues related to consumer gains. These alternatives focused on improving the products like the material, design, bags and cutting.

D. Prototype

The next phase is testing alternatives using prototypes developed in the previous process. In design thinking, testing was essential; the purpose was to determine how customers react to the prototype. Testing is your opportunity to receive feedback, develop your solution, and continue to learn about your users, Design Thinking Bootleg (2018).

Product Mock Up 1 - Headless Prayer Set Design (Travel size and Non-Travel Design)

The first product mockup design of the Leradia prayer set will possess a loose and straight cutting, making it appear simple and

attractive. It has a headless design, also known as a "poncho" design. Soft lightweight fabrics will be used, such as Premium Zara Silk, Sutra Armani Original, which is anti-wrinkle, anti-water stain, durable, shining, and keeps people cool while praying. This Prayer will be available in travel size and non-travel size, the material used for travel size one will be thinner with no transparency like Abutai/Premium Korean Parasut. This prayer set's overall look is feminine and elegant, making it suitable for daily use or special.

Figure 3. Leradia Product Mock-up 1

Product Mock Up 2 - One Set Elegant Headless Design Prayer Set

The second product mock-up design of the Leradia prayer set will also have a headless design, but in one set, the hijab and skirt will be separated. Soft lightweight fabrics will be used, such as Premium Armani, and Sutra, which are anti-wrinkle, anti-water stain, durable, shining and keep people cool while praying. This prayer set's overall look is more elegant, making it suitable for daily use or special days such as Ied Adha or Ied Fitri. The uniqueness of this design is that there will be Swarovski applied and in the neck side it is adjustable.

Figure 4. Leradia Product Mock-up 2

Product Mock Up 3 - One Set Elegant Laser Cut Design with Fastened Strap Prayer Set.

The third product mock-up design of the Leradia prayer set will be one set simple of the hijab and skirt. The uniqueness of this prayer set will have a fastened strap on the hijab side (like the masker strap) so it will be adjustable based on the head size of the consumer and will not lose. Soft lightweight fabrics will be used, such as Cotton, and Royal Silk which are anti-wrinkle, anti-water stain, durable, shining, and keep people cool while praying. This prayer set's overall look is more elegant, making it suitable for daily use or special days such as Ied Adha or Ied Fitri.

Figure 5. Leradia Product Mock-up 3

Product Mock Up 4 - One Set Elegant Lace Prayer Set

The fourth product mock-up design of the Leradia prayer set will be one set simple of the hijab and skirt. The uniqueness of this prayer set will have an elegant lace design under the hijab, skirt and in the middle of the hijab. Soft lightweight fabrics will be used, such as Cotton, and Royal Silk which are anti-wrinkle, anti-water stain, durable, shining, and keep people cool while praying. This prayer set's overall look is more elegant, making it suitable for daily use or special days such as Ied Adha or Ied Fitri.

Figure 6. Leradia Product Mock-up 4

E. Testing

The testing enables businesses to obtain user feedback on the developed concepts and to build more consumer empathy (Plattner, 2010). The final, but the most critical phase is testing. While this is the final phase, design thinking requires an iterative approach. This is the moment to demonstrate the prototype to users and get as much feedback as possible. Additionally, because the entire process is iterative, input from this stage can be used as critical data to return to the prior step.

This research will use one on one interviews with each informant that have been interviewed before from the Empathize phase with a total of 6 informants. This interview was conducted offline and online, depending on the availability of the informant. The questions in the interview focus on the target customer's preferred design based on the options provided, and they are asked for their comments as well as asked to rank the mock-up design. The customers then describe how they perceive the design and what design is suited for Leradia.

Based on the interview result, Leradia customers mostly choose Product Mock Up 3 - One Set Elegant Laser Cut Design with Fastened Strap Prayer Sets as the most preferred because it has a simple elegant design and has fastened strap on the head. The customer explained that this fastened strap can solve their problem, thus their hair will not be seen when praying because the size

will fit well to everyone's head and face size. It would be great if they have fastened the strap on the waist skirt as well. The second is Product Mock Up 1 - Headless Prayer Set Design (Travel size and Non-travel design). The third is Product Mock Up 4 - One Set Elegant Lace Prayer Set. And the fourth which the least liked by customers is Product Mock Up 2 - One Set Elegant Headless Design Prayer Set.

Leradia customers explained that when producing prayer sets no matter which design, they recommend the product with fastened strap on each design. And when using Swarovski-like Product Mock Up 2 - One Set Elegant Headless Design Prayer Set design, they explained that they like the design and represent Leradia so much, but it looks fragile when applied on a Prayer Set. They are afraid it will get off easily, thus Leradia must pay attention in choosing the Swarovski size and the stitching technique when using Swarovski accessories. Leradia customers have preferred colours on pastel colours, earth tone, and Neutral colors. About the bold colour it's the third option when there are no such preferred colours mentioned before. So this sweet pastel colour is the most preferred of Leradia customers. Thus Leradia should pay attention to choosing the colour when producing the prayer set.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this research, following the conclusion and answer to the research questions.

1. Leradia create new product development of Prayer Set product by adopted the Design Thinking approach to solve the problems with five stages to proceed with the data gathered. There are Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test. Qualitative methods are used by interviewing six of Leradia's most loyal customers to develop an understanding of Leradia's customer. In the empathize phase of design thinking using persona canvas, Leradia's customer have several pains and gains towards the prayer set product. When choosing a prayer set, they pay attention to the material that should be durable and gentle and give them coolness, elegant style, and a variety of colors from basic tone, earth tone, pastel tone to bold tone. For expected gain, customers expect unique details, like embroidered logo, metal stitching accent, or unique bag. Last, the customer's desired gain is eco-friendly, like zero-waste design. They will feel proud when knowing the product was zero-waste designed.

Since most of Leradia's customers have daily activities outside the home, they usually perform the Dhuhr and Ashar prayers outside the home. Thus, they must bring their own Prayer Set and Prayer Mat. Leradia customer's pain mainly came from undesired outcomes starting from unfitted cutting or unmatched size, uncomfortable material like stifflingly hot material, limited design option, not travel friendly design so they could not bring into small bags and also they did not provide prayer mat. The obstacles faced is that the picture that the seller posted on their social media sometimes is not the same with the real product, the expensive price, the colors offered is limited and sometimes it does not match customers' preference, and also the limited payment option.

2. The proposed strategy plan to create prayer set product development gained from Leradia's customers that contribute to the Prayer Set's long-term sales are by improving Leradia's prayer set products and services. The proposed services development are adding more sizes like XS, S, M, L, XL, and XXL with detailed sizing descriptions, providing consultation about sizing, sample product to try on, provide free service for cutting materials of Leradia prayer set, promotion, and membership card, create product reviews product picture and video, customer testimonials, installment payment service, and COD method, thank you card letter for supporting zero-waste design product, washing and care instructions, and activate online customer service.

For the proposed Leradia prayer set product development provides a variety of designs; A set of travel packages that consist of a set of prayer sets (skirt and hijab, and headless poncho practical prayer set) with prayer mat travel size and non-travel size with a variety of lace. Provides a variety of color tones and patterns, a variety of premium material, fastened by strap both on the hijab strap and strap at the waist of the skirt, so the size can be adjusted according to the size of the user. Provides unique bags, unique details and laser cutting design.

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